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Annotation: *This article examines the higher education system in the United States based on the analysis. The concept of "higher education system" is also the main goal is to meet the requirements of the time, high potential It is fundamental in the interpretation of important goals and tasks such as training specialists approaches are considered.*

Key words: *higher education, education system, loans, bachelor,*

The United States of America (USA) is made up of 50 states and one federal district is a federal republic. In addition, the United States is part of the Pacific Ocean A number of islands are included. Its area is 9.36 million km, and it is one of the largest countries in the world is one. The capital is Washington. The official language is English. 1 The United States offers unlimited opportunities for everyone is a state. The US has a stable economy, and the American education system is considered one of the best educational systems in the world. Education in the United States every foreign student who has graduated from the institutions has the right to stay and work there gets. He is sure of the high quality of the education system during his studies in the USA and will have medical assistance and social protection. Education program in the USA is one of the best educational programs in the world. Also a US student spends more money on education than any country in the world. This is US education is one of the reasons why the system is one of the best. In the report of countries for 2021, it should be noted that the best education The list of countries with the system includes:

1. United States of America
2. United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland
3. Germany
4. Canada
5. France
6. Switzerland
7. Japan \Australia
8. Sweden
9. The Netherlands is a country in Europe.

The American education system provides a rich alternative field for global students is enough.

State higher education system for admission to American higher education it is recommended to have information about. This is an educational process in its own right to learn more about the steps and results gives the opportunity. The academic year lasts an average of 4 years and the student receives a bachelor's degree. If the student has a bachelor's degree, the master's degree lasts 1.5-2 years. Doctoral studies 2-4 years. The educational institutions of the USA are full of students offers specialties. Usually, most foreign students study business, management, they choose areas such as engineering and mathematics. American higher education is one of the main features of their country, without choosing a specialty at once, one or the possibility of choosing after two-year general education courses. When applying for studies, where are the requirements for: university, preparatory course or college differs depending on the submission. At the same time, every foreign student knows English must have IELTS or TOEFL certificates confirming the level. A distinctive feature of the American higher education system is that the student studies the ability to change its "primary" direction several times during. Americans often use this opportunity. This means that the highest in the process of obtaining information, the student begins to like another specialty, and in this regard American universities are very flexible. Classes at universities differ from each other: to several hundred students from large intended lectures to small lessons for a few students and to seminars (discussions). The atmosphere in American university classrooms is very lively You can express your opinion, defend your point of view, you are allowed to participate in discussions and prepare presentations. Exactly these aspects often surprise foreign students in the USA. Teachers grade each student during the course. Usually, evaluation depends on the following factors:

- each teacher has his own requirements: students in lectures and seminars This is an important factor in the final grade for the course.
- the midterm exam usually takes place during class.
- to evaluate you must pass one or more essay or laboratory work.
- short exams or tests will be held. Sometimes teachers are unexpected they give tests. They are not taken into account in scoring, but reading students and used to encourage participation.
- the final exam was held after the last lesson of the course.

Credits

Each course "consumes" a certain number of credits or credit hours. This is approximately equal to the number of hours taught in a class per week. Usually 3-5 per course credit is taken into account. In most universities, the semester program is 12-15 credits consists of (3-5 subjects in one semester). A certain amount to get a diploma of education must "collect" credits. 2 Opportunities to live in the US Campus and dormitories are the most convenient and optimal for living and studying are residential places with conditions. Usually, campuses are attached to educational institution or is located in their territory, and it is much more expensive than private sectors It is

considered cheap. American dormitories are a building consisting of mixed housings and all students live in one building, but on different floors or buildings Kitchen and bathroom are usually shared on the floor. Rooms are needed it will be equipped with furniture, TV, internet. Living in a dormitory one of the advantages is the presence of <<social areas>>. Here students are one meeting each other, organizing various games, watching TV, etc they can talk. Living expenses average around \$600 per month, and additional costs are costs such as food, drinking water, room cleaning includes. Payment is made once per semester.

CONCLUSION

My conclusion from this article is that the United States of America is different can offer a lot to the student: the most prestigious higher education in the world one of the systems, eclectic cities and wonderful natural parks, many ethnic groups a unique culture that unites. Studying in the USA gives students not only degrees and a diploma, but also experience, which is very important, and gives them a bright future prepares The flexibility of educational programs, as well as their various social adaptation to needs:

- different forms of education;
- higher democratic educational processes;
- the freedom of the student to choose the study program and form.

American applicants to several universities at the same time will be given the opportunity to submit documents. This significantly increases the chances of acceptance increases. Such opportunities and reforms are being implemented in Uzbekistan. American education system for the further development of scientific and technical progress It is distinguished by its flexibility and ability to change. Such a system prepares excellent specialists in the field. American education is one of the most effective and prestigious industries in the world. The majority people dream of studying in the USA, but often the cost of studying high does not allow to achieve these possibilities. For example, George Washington university, almost 40,500 for each academic year dollars, excluding textbooks and living expenses.

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